

The Science of Geoengineering

SPICE project (Stratospheric Particle Injection for Climate Engineering)

British lead research investigates the impact and feasibility of a proposed geoengineering solution.

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Hello and welcome to the November 2011 newsletter!

Welcome to another bumper addition of the EPG newsletter.

Our front cover illustration tells us about geoengineering, which was the topic of the evening lecture from this year's Environmental Physics Day. A report of the members section of the meeting can be found on page 9. Reports of other EPG related events include the two day conference to mark the 150th anniversary of the publication of Tyndall's work on the trapping of IR energy by greenhouse gases, and a joint meeting about renewable energy with the Energy Institute and the Institute of Chemical Engineers.

The EPG has held several successful events with other societies, and if you have an idea of an event you would like to run, either with another society or as a stand alone event, please let one of the group officers know. Our calendar is quite quiet over the winter, so we welcome offers from members to come involved.

This year we held another successful environmental physics essay competition, we had so many excellent entries that we had to award a tie for first place. Prizes were awarded in May at Environmental Physics Day. The two essays that won were both excellent with nothing to choose between them, so the first prize was jointly awarded to Gabriel Davies with the essay, "Why Physics Should Decide the Future of Transport" and to Thomas Smith whose essay was entitled "Not just recycled sunlight: Biomass burning and its influence on global climate change". They were both awarded £150. The runner-up (£100) was Emily Adlam for her essay "Talking About Communication", while finally a highly commended prize of £25 was awarded to William Parker for his essay on "Nuclear Power". Well done! For details of this year's competition, please go to page 6.

We hope you enjoy the newsletter.

Sally Brown and Hugh Mortimer

EPG News

A message from Pat Goodman, the Chair of the EPG

Dear Colleagues,

We have had another very busy year, with a wide range of events and talks, all of which have been well received. We have already had two excellent newsletters which are a real credit to our editors, Sally Brown and Hugh Mortimer.

In May we had our annual event for members and AGM. Environmental Physics Day has now become a permanent event on our calendar, and the attendances have been increasing year on year. In 2012, Environmental Physics Day will be held on Wednesday 30th May, and again we will have an evening lecture in conjunction with the London and South East branch.

In our last newsletter and at our AGM, I raised our concerns about the IOP rules on the length of time one can spend on an IOP committee. The EPG is concerned that a lifetime committee membership of nine years is limiting, and in the case of active younger committee members, the IOP rules state they would have to step down, say in their mid 30s and not be allowed to participate for the remainder of their careers. Following the AGM and at the request of the members, I wrote to the IOP on this very matter and asked that it be debated at Council. I have not had the courtesy of an acknowledgement from the IOP, let alone a reply. I am following up on this as I believe that it is an extremely important issue for all IOP members and groups. Clearly it is good for groups to have a turnover in committee members and to get new blood in. We fully support this, but excluding people who are specialist in the subject area for the remainder of their careers is not justifiable.

I mentioned above the poor (lack) of communication from IOP, and again our committee have asked that I bring these matters to the attention of the IOP secretary. The group have been very proactive at working with the IOP to provide responses to surveys, feedback on policy documents, career profiles etc. Some of these get taken onboard, others seem to vanish into *black holes!* I will be asking that a better service be provided to members in this regard.

I am aware that there have been some problems with the IOP web pages, and that events do not seem to appear on the relevant calendars, I understand that IOP are addressing this.

Again, could I encourage you to work with the Group in providing a service to you as members. We have tried to work with the various IOP branches so that we have EPG events in the various regions, and we have teamed up with other societies such as the Royal Met Soc, the Aerosol Society, Institute for Chemical Engineers and the Energy Institute to provide joint events. We plan to continue with these activities (for a report on our recent joint event, see page 13). Our events calendar is rather quiet for the first few months of 2012, so if you have any suggestions for events that the group can be involved with, either jointly or as a standalone event, please contact any of the officers – contact details can be found on the back pages of the newsletter.

Finally I would like to thank all of the committee for their hard work on your behalf over the past year. I also want to thank those who had to step down at the AGM after 9+ years of service (Karen Aplin, Peter Hodgson, Ian Colbeck), and also those who chose to retire (Curtis Wood, Alison Buckley). Finally I welcome two new committee members, Simon Buckle and Jarlath Molloy. You can find more about Simon and Jarlath on page 8.

Sincerely

Pat

The 7th Annual Environmental Physics Group Essay Competition.

Closing date – 31st December 2011

Entries are now invited for this year's EPG Essay Competition. The aim of the competition is to encourage and recognise excellence in communicating the significance, value and rewarding nature of engaging with environmental physics. Entries should cover any aspect encompassed by the Group's interests in environmental physics, which include, but are not limited to: atmosphere and climate; hydrology; plant physics; glaciology; waste; energy; the built environment.

- **prize money totals £500;**
- a certificate will also be awarded to the winning author(s);
- the winning entries will be considered for publication;
- all entrants will be **offered 3 months free membership** of the IOP;

- the competition is **open to all**, but entries from students are particularly welcome;
- essays must be **no more than 2,000 words** long;
- the closing date is **31st December 2011**.

Entries must be original and will be judged on writing quality and content. Essays adopting a purely scientific, policy-related or some other perspective will be welcomed. It is anticipated that presentations will be made by the winning author(s) at the Group's Environmental Physics meeting on Wednesday 30th May 2012.

Entries should be sent to: env.essay@physics.org, preferably as a pdf file, along with full contact details and student status if appropriate. Entries may be also be submitted by post to:

Environmental Physics Group (essay competition),
c/o Science Support Officer,
The Institute of Physics,
76 Portland Place,
London. W1B 1NT

Further details are available on the Group's web site or from env.essay@physics.org.

Environmental Physics Group. Secretary's Report: 2010-2011 20th Annual General Meeting, 25th May 2011

Membership

There has been a 9% growth in the Group's membership, up to 700 members today from 643 at the 2010 AGM. Therefore, the Group's membership numbers appear to be very healthy.

The Committee met four times: on 26 May 2010 in London with 13 attendees; on 15 September 2010 in London with 10 attendees; on 24 November 2010 in London with 11 attendees; and on 17 March 2011 in Edinburgh with 6 attendees. The AGM was held on 26 May 2010 in London with 33 attendees

Committee Composition

The committee composition (before May's elections) is listed below.

<i>Name</i>	<i>Status</i>	<i>Last elected</i>	<i>Expiry</i>
Pat Goodman (Chair)	Officer	2010	2013
Karen Aplin (Vice Chair & Treasurer)	Officer	2010	2011
Paul Williams (Hon Secretary)	Officer	2009	2012
Ian Colbeck	Ordinary	2009	2011
Peter Hodgson	Ordinary	2010	2011
Sally Brown	Ordinary	2007	2011
Curtis Wood	Ordinary	2008	2011
Alison Buckley	Ordinary	2010	2011
Giles Harrison	Ordinary	2010	2013
Alec Bennett	Ordinary	2009	2013
Hugh Mortimer	Ordinary	2009	2013
Mhairi Coyle	Ordinary	2010	2013
Christopher Lavers	Ordinary	2010	2013

Many thanks are owed to all the committee members for their dedicated service.

Paul Williams
Honorary Secretary
May 2011

Profile of EPG Committee Members

We have taken the opportunity to find out a little more about our two new EPG committee members elected in May - Simon Buckle and Jarlath Molloy.

Simon Buckle is Climate Policy Director at the Grantham Institute at Imperial College London and, from 1st October, the College's Pro-Rector for International Affairs. He studied Physics and Philosophy at Bristol University before taking a DPhil in low-temperature physics at Sussex University. After a year as a researcher in quantum optics at Imperial, he joined the UK Diplomatic Service in 1986 and spent the next twenty years or so in a variety of different roles in the UK and overseas, including a spell as an economist at the Bank of England. Simon has been a Fellow of the IoP since 2001.

Jarlath recently completed a PhD at Imperial College London, where his research focused on options to reduce aviation's environmental impact. Previously he undertook an MSc in climate change at the University of East Anglia and studied applied physics at the Dublin Institute of Technology. Jarlath is presently a consultant in the environment branch with ICAO.

Reports from EPG Previous Events

Environmental Physics Day

Institute of Physics, London

Wednesday 25th May 2011

Environmental Physics Day was held on Wednesday 25th May 2011 in the Philips Room, at the Institute of Physics, London. It took the form of a set of science presentations, ending with short talks from prize winners of the EPG Essay competition. There were 38 attendees, and the talks were chaired by Patrick Goodman and Chris Lavers. As with all previous Environmental Physics Days the speakers presented their own personal perspectives, which do not necessarily represent the views of the Institute of Physics or the Environmental Physics Group.

In the first talk, Terri Jackson presented a selection of review material under the title *Climate Change- Natural, man-made or both?* She looked primarily at the

relationship between variations in observed global temperature and CO₂, emphasising the variability exhibited from recognised data sources. She argued that data from the Hadley Centre showed no clear correlation between world temperature and CO₂ increase on inter-annual timescales, rather, that satellite based temperature data, specifically the latest Global Sea Surface Temperature data showed a -0.1 to 0.2 degree reduction (over the past few years). She made a further point that paleo evidence showed temperature changes occurring before CO₂ out gassing (from Antarctic measurements), with a time lag of up to 1600 years. She drew attention to past cyclic variations in solar irradiance only being inferred rather than directly measured (*e.g.* Shapiro *et al.* Astronomy and Astrophysics 529 A67 (2011) 24 February 2011), on which basis she said it was possible that solar irradiance was up to 6 times greater than assumed by the IPCC. This remarkable claim, and many other aspects of her talk provoked a variety of challenges from the audience, some concerning its basic assumptions.

Dr Salvatore Pascale (University of Reading) presented *Thermodynamics of the climate system*. He gave an introduction to non-equilibrium steady states of entropy by irreversible processes, with the steady state maintained by balancing input/output energy with entropy. A climate system can be viewed as a heat engine with entropy production as a fundamental property of the system - a measure of the irreversibility of a system. Maximum entropy production is analysed theoretically with a Lorentz cycle and Carnot engine. To evaluate a climate's energy budget it is necessary to know the total kinetic and potential energies. Carnot heat engines consider a hot/cold reservoir generating mechanical work. Dr Pascale compared the entropy at the top of the atmosphere with the entropy increase from radiation and fluid dynamics. Models such as HadCM3 can look at defining climate systems' thermodynamics, and analyse the parametric sensitivity to provide climate feedback information. Dr Pascale showed a sensitivity study lasting 8000 years with a "solar constant" $\pm 10\%$ of the modern value. Thermodynamic efficiency was investigated with various conversion efficiency scenarios. Colder climates proved more efficient at converting energy into mechanical work, with a climate sensitivity experiment increasing CO₂ up to 1750ppm. He suggested that the use of such thermodynamic tools, of which the entropy budget is very important, can provide constraints on modelling future likely climate scenarios. Future planetary climate tipping points tend to prefer those maximising entropy. The challenge is to include biosphere-climate interactions, and to consider the dynamics of other planetary atmospheres.

Dr Simon Buckle, (Grantham Institute for Climate Change, Imperial College) introduced new concepts about climate economics: *Climate mitigation: sustainable preferences and cumulative carbon*. Dr Buckle looked at peak warming correlated with cumulative carbon and possible mitigation options available to developed and developing economies. The anticipated requirement to reduce energy demands against a projected 2 to 3-fold increase in the short term

was considered. The question raised was how society would meet such demands? Target figures for 2050 were presented: renewables 6%, nuclear 17% etc., with the nuclear element open to scrutiny in light of recent developments in Japan. A further pertinent question was - How fast should we act, given perceived disjunction between scientists and economists? Three issues are often raised: ethics, the representation of damage and the risk of extreme/irreversible changes. The presentation focused on the first two factors. Previous policy conclusions for sustainability preferences providing long term as well as short term benefits, dividing productivity (emissions) between consumption and long term discounted consumption. Optimising solutions are needed as the 'business as usual' scenario is unsustainable. Adoption of clean technologies may increase the business *growth envelope*: although it doesn't reduce CO₂, but does make mitigation feasible. In summary, sustainable preferences affect cumulative carbon and present a fundamental ethical choice. Clean technologies potentially make targets *feasible* to achieve, so why is climate policy so difficult? Variations in political or social systems globally, across rich and poor, developed and developing, are constrained by the 'Carbon Pie' of who gets what, and depend on *actual* emissions matching what is reported. It was concluded that, for measures to be effective, an element is required more akin to arms control than simply legislation with discussion of appropriate assumptions for such modelling.

Dr Helen Dacre (Department of Meteorology, University of Reading) described her work comparing the modelled distribution of volcanic ash from the eruption of Eyjafjallajökull in April and May of 2010 with disparate observations. This work felt particularly timely as, not only was it almost exactly one year on, but because Environmental Physics Day itself (25th May 2011) took place during the eruption of another Icelandic volcano, Grimsvötn, which was affecting European airspace. During the period 14th to 20th April 2010, 75 % of European airspace was closed leading to the cancellation of 100,000 flights, as there was then a zero tolerance to ash. For the 2011 episode, a more sophisticated high (>4 mg m⁻³), medium (2 to 0.2 mg m⁻³) and low (<0.2 mg m⁻³) categorisation was adopted. This new approach requires quantitative predictions of ash concentrations, rather than just identifying zones where ash is expected. These quantitative needs have been met from the validation of the Met Office's NAME dispersal model. The validation comparisons were made with a range of measurements taken during the 2010 Icelandic eruption, during which a feature of the meteorological conditions was the abundance of clear skies, permitting many measurements of the ash plume above. Using Lidar and *in situ* observations, Dr Dacre showed that about 3% by mass of the ash emitted originally ended up in particles with diameters less than 100 microns at over 1000 km from the source, a quantity known as the Distal Fine Ash Fraction. This fraction was well constrained by the different measurements, and provides the basis for quantitative predictions for the Grimsvötn eruption plume dispersal, when combined with empirical relationships for the eruption source term based on observed plume height.

In her talk on *unforeseen societal consequences of bioelectromagnetics*, Mrs Anne Silk (John Radcliffe Hospital, Oxford) listed a range of possible human effects of electromagnetic radiation. In the domestic environment, Digitally Enhanced Cordless Telephones (DECT) may generate adverse health effects in some individuals. This could be a result of the pulsing of radio frequency energy emitted, stimulating susceptible parts of the brain. In support of this, an anecdotal example was given of an individual whose symptoms had ceased immediately after a standard landline had replaced a DECT device, but then suddenly recurred whilst visiting a different dwelling having a DECT. Modern materials used in audio headphones, notably neodymium for magnets, also bring concerns, because of the intense local magnetic fields which can be generated near to the head. It is known that eddy currents and local heating can occur in the brain, which, if affecting a particularly sensitive region, might provide the basis with which to explain some spontaneous acts of violence. As the human head shows a resonant response around 900MHz, where there are multiple UHF radio sources, “hot spots” could arise resulting in particularly adverse human health effects.

Ms Sotira Trifourki (the Greater Manchester STEM Centre, University of Salford), described a range of classroom initiatives for environmental physics education. In astro-visualisations, for example, models and data are used to generate accurate depictions of astronomical phenomena. With partner agencies such as the European Space Agency and the European Southern Observatory, datasets are available to generate engaging visualisations. In the classroom context these generate fundamental questions in response, such as “Can we predict earthquakes?”, and “Is climate change reversible?”, illustrating the thought-provoking consequences of the visualisations. Real environmental problems are particularly appealing subjects, and generating awareness of light pollution is especially relevant to astronomical awareness. For younger school children, a method of measuring how effective these approaches are is to ask them to draw pictures to describe their knowledge state, before and after. Favourable results in knowledge transfer can therefore be demonstrated. Other techniques described included “Live Disaster”, in which a role play workshop was used to allow students to re-enact disaster scenarios using satellite data.

Chris Lavers and Giles Harrison

The greenhouse effect and global warming: celebrating the work of John Tyndall

Dublin Castle, Dublin, Ireland

Wednesday September 28th to Friday 30th September 2011

The two day conference to mark the 150th anniversary of the publication of Tyndall's work on the trapping of IR energy by greenhouse gases, held in the splendid buildings of Dublin Castle on the 28th-30th of September was a great success. The conference was attended by over 120 delegates. The event received significant media coverage with articles on the BBC and in the local Irish TV news.

The event was jointly organized by the Royal Irish Academy, (Climate Change Sciences Committee) and the Irish EPA. Funding provided by the ESA and the Environmental Physics Group was associated with the event. Speaking after the event, Prof. Ray Bates (RIA CCSC Chair) was delighted with the attendance. The event has helped to raise the awareness and profile of Tyndall in the Climate Science arena.

The conference was fortunate in having quite a number of high profile international speakers (details of speakers and topics (<http://tyndallconference2011.org/>)) The evening before the conference a public lecture was delivered by Prof. Richard Somerville, which was extremely well attended. In addition Prof. Somerville was interviewed on Irish National radio, and spoke about Tyndall's work. He was asked a number of questions on controversial aspects of climate change, and he gave very clear answers that were appropriate for a general audience.

One of the highlights of the conference was the display of original Tyndall experimental apparatus which was kindly made available for the conference.

Prof Sommerville will have a paper on his presentation published in a forthcoming issue of the American Meteorological Society Bulletin. His public lecture is also now available on YouTube:

http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5maT2CunT08&feature=channel_video_title

Ray Bates, University College Dublin and chair of the Scientific Advisory Committee for the Tyndall Conference

Renewable energy generation in the water industry

National Metals Technology Centre, Rotherham

Wednesday 14 September 2011

Organised by the EPG, Energy Institute and the Institute of Chemical Engineers.

The water industry as a whole is one of the largest consumers of electricity in the UK, using approximately 8TWh annually. This is about 2% of the UK's total consumption and costs the water companies in the region of £600M per annum. Electricity consumption is used approximately equally between water supply and waste water functions, with at least 80% of the total being used for pumping water or sewage, or blowing air for activated sludge processes.

In this talk, Richard Hall, formerly of Yorkshire Water, compared the industry's electricity consumption with its potential to generate electricity, with a particular emphasis on different generating technologies and the current policy framework. At the present time, the water industry generates approximately 10% of its own electricity needs, but there is potential for this figure to go much higher. The drivers are several, but most significant are financial, including cost certainty in an energy market where costs can fluctuate significantly. Applicable technologies include hydro-electric (e.g Archimedean screw), and increasingly Combined Heat & Power (CHP) using biogas from sewage sludge.

Installation costs are often high, but there are a range of policy incentives and subsidies that make schemes more viable. The speaker discussed the most relevant of these, including Renewable Obligation Certificates (ROCs), Feed-in Tariffs (FITs) and the Renewable Heating Incentive. However, some of these schemes have conditions that limit their application within the water industry, for

example ROCs and FITs are not allowable for some types of hydro-electric schemes. The speaker's conclusion was that the regulation governing electricity generation is complex and inconsistent when applied to the water industry and that this is hampering the further development of significant generation potential.

Thirty people attended this meeting, the second in a series of joint meetings between the Environmental Physics Group, the Institute of Chemical Engineers and the Energy Institute.

Peter Hodgson

Forthcoming Environmental Physics Group Events

Visit to the Thames Barrier

Woolwich, Central London

Wednesday 14th December 2011, 12.30-3.00.

The Thames Barrier was officially opened in 1984 and is the world's largest flood barrier at 520m long. At a cost of £0.5 billion to build, the barrier offers vital protection to 125km² of central London and protects 1.25 million people from flooding. The Environmental Physics Group has booked exclusive use of the Information Centre on Wednesday 14th December, where we will be provided with a tour and talk of the facilities. The talk will include the history of the river and the risk of flooding in London, as well as describing the environment and

wildlife of the Thames. A light lunch will also be provided. To assist with catering costs, members are kindly asked to contribute £6.50.

Places are limited and **must** be booked in advance (please do not just turn up on the day). For booking your place, further information (including details about payment), please contact with Sally Brown (sb20@soton.ac.uk) no later than Thursday 24th November 2011. In your email, please can state if you have any special dietary requirements.

Sailors, sea-dogs and storms: how old naval documents help us to understand climatic change.

Dr Dennis Wheeler, University of Sunderland

Henry Charnock Lecture Theatre, National Oceanography Centre (NOC), Southampton

Thursday 23rd February 2012, 6pm (refreshments) for a 6.30pm start

Organised by the Environmental Physics Group, South Central Branch and Tyndall Centre for Climate Change Research at Southampton.

The UK has a uniquely rich heritage of Royal Navy logbooks, many from as early as the late 17th century. Over the past few years an international team of researchers has been abstracting the wealth of climate information that they contain. This information is now being used to help scientists understand the nature of past climate change and to assist in producing better forecasts of what the future might hold.

To assist with catering, please register for this event by 15th February 2012 by contacting Sally Brown (sb20@soton.ac.uk), stating if you are a member of the South Central Branch or the Environmental Physics Group.

Directions to the NOC may be found <http://www.soton.ac.uk/visitus/campuses/nocs.html> Please note if you are driving to NOC, you go through the manned dock security (don't be put off by this, you aren't going the wrong way!). If you are planning to arrive by car before 6pm, please mention this in your registration email.

Environmental Physics Day 2012

IOP London

Wednesday 30th May 2012

As in previous years we will hold our annual meeting and evening lecture on the same day and members are invited to attend and discuss environmental physics. We are presently in the early stages of planning, so we have no details yet, just a date to add into your diary. Please look out for details in the next newsletter.

Forthcoming IOP Events

Stand-up for start-ups: Getting low carbon technologies off the ground

Institute of Physics, London

Monday 14th November 2011

Organised by the Energy Group

This one day event at the Institute of Physics showcases seven of the latest privately funded physics-based start up companies and provides insight into the challenges faced in bringing new low-carbon inventions to the market.

A diverse range of products will be covered: thermal storage, batteries, liquid air, PV, sensors for power generators, LED lighting, and DC distribution

Physics and physicists have an important part to play in developing technologies for sustainable energy and efficient use. With rising energy prices, concepts and technologies from the laboratory are gaining commercial interest and attracting private finance.

The aim of the day is to communicate the contribution that physics and physicists are making to solve one of the world's major challenges and would be of relevance to anyone interested in the commercial application of physics, including students, researchers, energy companies, funders, investors, inventors, and policy-makers.

The programme allows for plenty of time for discussion with the speakers and within the audience.

For event information, take a look at the IOP events website:
<http://www.iop.org/events/scientific/conferences/y/11/carbon/>

Photon12

University of Durham

Monday 3rd – Thursday 6th September 2012

Photon12 is the largest optics conference in the UK. Photon12 will comprise:

- Optics and Photonics 2012 the biennial conference of the IOP Optics and Photonics Division. The conference includes sessions representing the Groups of the Division, and from the Fringe Analysis Special Interest Group.
- QEP-20 the latest in the series of conferences initiated in 1973 by the IOP Quantum Electronics and Photonics Group.
- An Industry Technology Programme: sessions of particular interest to those in the optics industry.
- An exhibition of the latest optics and photonics technology
- Plenary Lectures
- Tutorials and summer schools

Abstract submission deadline: 28th February 2012

Early registration deadline: 27th July 2012

Registration deadline: 29th August 2012

More information about the conference can be found via the link on the Institute's conference homepage: <http://www.iop.org/events/scientific/conferences/>

International Conference on Neutron Scattering

Edinburgh International Conference Centre

Monday 8th – Friday 12th July 2013

ICNS 2013 will bring together scientists from a wide range of disciplines including biology, chemistry, earth science, engineering, materials science and physics. This international conference is held every four years, and abstracts are not due until 15th February 2013, so plenty of time to get your thinking caps on!

Energy and Low Carbon Technology Conference - Measurement Makes Business Sense

Central London

18th – 19th September 2013

Jointly run by the IOP, this programme comprises 5 parallel streams, plus plenary sessions covering research and development, advances in technology and instrumentation, applied measurement and metrology, measurement infrastructure and training.

For more information, see the conference website:

http://www.tuvnel.com/tuvnel/energy_and_low_carbon_technology_conference

Other forthcoming Events

Atmospheric research from balloon – “Research Radiosondes”

Dr Keri Nicholl, University of Reading.

Reading Town Hall, Victoria Gallery, Reading, Berkshire

Wednesday 30th November 2011, 7pm.

Balloons have been used as a tool for atmospheric research for many years, to which the discovery of atmospheric layering, cosmic rays and the charge structure of thunderstorms are due. The invention of radiosondes in the 1920s allowed data to be sent back to the surface in real time, removing the requirements for human pilots and sonde recovery. Nowadays radiosondes are launched regularly from more than 800 locations around the world, mostly for operational weather forecasting. As well as their operational uses, radiosondes can also provide an airborne platform for new atmospheric research, particularly in regions deemed too hazardous for manned aircraft to fly.

This talk will give an overview of Research Radiosondes, including details of the specialist sensors used and results obtained from balloon flights in a variety of atmospheric phenomena, including cloud, volcanic ash from the Icelandic Eyjafjallajökull eruption, and Saharan dust.

This meeting is free. All are welcome, but seats are limited, so please arrive early to be sure of a place! This talk is organised by the Royal Meteorological Society. For more information, please contact: RMetS.SE@gmail.com

29th IUGG Conference on Mathematical Geophysics

National Museum of Scotland, Edinburgh

Monday 18th – Friday 22nd June 2012

This conference is jointly sponsored by the IOP Environmental Physics Group and the Nonlinear and Complex Physics Group.

- Contributions are invited from all areas of mathematical geoscience.
- The conference programme has a range of cross-cutting themes aimed at raising discussion between scientists from different disciplines.
- Topics include earth observation, earth system dynamics, crustal dynamics, geophysical fluid dynamics, atmosphere-ocean dynamics, rationalising models with observations and solving geophysical problems.
- Registration opens 1st November 2011.
- For more information, see the conference website:
<http://www.cmgedinburgh2012.org.uk/>

Earth Systems Engineering 2012

Newcastle University

Tuesday 3rd to Thursday 5th July 2012

The potential of technology to help solve many of the world's most pressing problems, ranging from climate change to resource scarcity and poverty, is widely recognised. However, rationally managing and engineering the Earth's systems is a hugely complex task. *Earth Systems Engineering 2012* will explore how engineering decisions can better respond to the challenges of intensifying global change. These challenges include long term changes (e.g. in the climate, land use and human behaviour), societal interactions (e.g. between the built environment, transport demand and greenhouse gas emissions) and many other uncertainties. Submissions are sought for the following symposium themes:

- *Cities and Infrastructure*
- *Catchment and coastal management*
- *Engineering within resource constraints*
- *Geoengineering*
- *Modelling of coupled human, natural and technological systems*
- *Foresight and understanding long term change*
- *Decision-making and management of complex systems*

Symposium fees including accommodation and meals will be funded for all delegates, but numbers are strictly limited to 40 people who will be invited on the basis of abstract submissions. A few travel bursaries are available, with priority for developing country and early career researchers. Applicants must apply at <http://conferences.ncl.ac.uk/ese2012/> before 16th December 2011.

Planned events of the Environmental Physics Group

At each committee meeting, committee members discuss what events we think are topical, and what members would like to see. Response and interaction between the committee and members is essential to achieve the correct balance of activities. For those who completed the Group's survey last winter, the help was much appreciated and the data helped us envisage future potential topics. To this end, we have compiled a list of potential planned events. With changes to the committee rules we have lost a number of active and valuable committee members, and would like to hear from members who feel that they are able to organise an event, or contribute ideas. A list of potential topics is below.

- a) Media reporting of environmental events: joint with Physics Communicators Group
- b) Centenary of cosmic rays: joint with Particle Physics Group
- c) Climate Change and Health: half-day meeting in Dublin
- d) Visit to the Energy Recovery Facility in Sheffield
- e) Olympics and weather, joint with RMetS
- f) Research Ethics: an evening meeting with a philosopher
- g) Environmental radioactivity
- h) Joint event with SCI Environment Group, on radioactivity and drinking water
- i) Climate adaptation and energy use
- j) EMFs and human effects

If you have any thoughts about these topics, feel that you can help in the organisation, or would like to volunteer to present (or know someone who would), please contact the Group Secretary, Paul Williams p.d.williams@reading.ac.uk (for full details, see the back of the newsletter). We also welcome other ideas and topics.

Other Activities

Environmental Physics Letters

Guillaume Wright is the publishing editor of Environmental Research Letters. Here he tells us a little more about the IOP journal.

Environmental Research Letters (ERL) is a high-impact, broad scope open-access research journal (2010 Impact Factor: 3.049) intended as the meeting-place of the research and policy communities concerned with environmental change and management. ERL publishes both Letters reporting new and original research of outstanding quality and Perspectives, commissioned commentaries highlighting the impact and wider environmental implications of research appearing in ERL. All articles published in ERL are also guaranteed coverage by our widely-read sister community website, *environmentalresearchweb.org*.

The journal's coverage reflects the increasingly interdisciplinary nature of environmental science, recognizing the wide-ranging contributions to the development of methods, tools and evaluation strategies relevant to the field. Submissions from across all components of the Earth system, i.e. land, atmosphere, cryosphere, biosphere and hydrosphere (freshwater and marine), and exchanges between these components are welcome. The core of ERL's content draws from observations, numerical modelling, theoretical and experimental approaches to environmental science, and especially science relevant to policy, impacts, and decision-making. In addition, approaches from a range of physical and natural sciences, economics, and political, sociological and legal studies are strongly encouraged.

Volunteers needed for Lab in a Lorry in the south east

Lab in a Lorry, the Institute's mobile science lab for young people, will be touring schools in the south east of England this autumn to try and connect young people in the region to science. Lab in a Lorry needs volunteers to guide visitors through the on board experiments. You will be sent information on the experiments and there will be a training session each morning. For more details see http://www.iop.org/activity/branches/south_east/lse/news/11/july/page_51526.html

Interactions

Remember that *Interactions*, the Institute's round up of events and news went digital last February. Find it online by logging onto MyIOP, and find the link on the left hand side.

For those of you who enjoy reading (or experimenting!) the Marvin and Milo cartoon, a new book on the 'Do try this at home' has been published. The cartoons were devised so that children can easily understand them, with additional text in the book that explains the science behind the experiment. Co-author of the book, and the Institute's head of public engagement Caitlin Watson said, "It's suitable for people such as parents, grandparents, teachers, leaders of youth groups and children themselves. My hope for the book is that people will buy it and do the experiments".

'Marvin and Milo Adventures in Science' costs £9.99 and is available to buy in bookshops and online.

South West Region photography competition

This competition is open to all IOP members and its affiliated schools that live, study or work in the South West region. The theme is "Physics in the South West." For example, this could involve; Physicists from the South West, research completed at Universities in the region, discoveries made in the South West or simply demonstrations of physical phenomena in front of landmarks in the area.

Submit a photo **you have taken** and a caption of no more than 200 words explaining how your photo relates to the theme to iop.sw.photos@gmail.com by the 1 February 2012.

Prizes: 1st place- an Amazon Kindle, 2nd place- £25 Jessops Vouchers

For more information and rules, see

http://www.iop.org/activity/branches/south_west/sw/news/11/page_52238.html

Research Student Conference Fund

Each year the group is allocated funds for students to apply for financial assistance to attend environmental-physics related international conferences and major national meetings. We are pleased to sponsor students at events such as these, and students are welcome to apply for up to £250 during the course of their studies. Please see the advert below for further details.

Supporting research students

Research Student Conference Fund

Providing financial support to research student members, to attend international conferences and major national meetings.

Apply for up to £250 during the course of your PhD.

Applications are considered on a quarterly basis and should reach the Institute by: 1 March, 1 June, 1 September or 1 December

For further information see www.iop.org or contact supportandgrants@iop.org

IOP Institute of Physics

‘Physics for All’ campaign launches

The Institute has launched a campaign, “Physics for All”, aimed at encouraging members to emphasise the importance of good physics education in schools in their area. For more information, look up: http://www.iop.org/news/11/sept/page_51922.html

Becoming chartered and Fellowship status of the IOP

Once again, the IOP are running a series of chartership workshops around the country aimed at providing information and answering any questions you may have about the application process. The workshops cover:

- *The benefits of getting chartered*
- *The two designations (CPhys and CEng) offered by the Institute and the differences between them*
- *The requirements and application process*
- *Making an effective application*

The workshops will take place:

November 2 nd 6.30pm	London	The Institute of Physics, 76 Portland Place, London W1B 1NT
November 10 th 6.30pm	Aberdeen	Copthorne Aberdeen, 122 Huntly Street, Aberdeen, AB10 1SU
November 30 th 6.30pm	Birmingham	Copthorne Hotel Birmingham, Paradise Circus, Birmingham B3 3HJ

The IOP is also holding a general CPD workshop entitled **How to do CPD...And why you should** to be held on December 6th at 6.30 in Portland Place, London.

Workshops are free of charge and are open to IOP members only; places are limited and must be booked. If you are interested in attending one of these workshops, please email CPD@iop.org along with your membership number stating which workshop you would like to attend.

We are also planning an event in London regarding Fellowship status. Please contact CPD@iop.org if you would like any further information.

Online learning

IOP members can access nearly 30 award-winning online transferable skills courses, free of charge. Categories include

- Business thinking
- HR and compliance
- Managing people
- Personal effectiveness
- Professional skills
- Sales skills

See http://www.iop.org/membership/prof-dev/tools/learning/page_38201.html for further details.

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This newsletter is also available on the web and in larger print sizes

The contents of this newsletter do not necessarily represent the views or policies of the Institute of Physics, except where explicitly stated.

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